

EDITORIAL

Why is Infertility So High Among Couples Nowadays?

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Literature data have shown that infertility affects about 15% of couples, but according to the author's experience, observing the changes in the energy characteristics of our population in recent years, very well documented in the article *Energy Alterations and Chakras' Energy Deficiencies and Propensity to SARSCoV-2 Infection*, where the author (2021) explains that almost all her patients are without energy in the internal organs, which in Chinese medicine, are responsible for the production of energy for health maintenance and also, among other functions, reproduction [1,2].

This subject was the theme taken by the author in a presentation at the 3rd International Conference on Gynecology and Obstetrics, that was held in Osaka, Japan, in June 2019, whose title was *Chakras' Energy Deficiency as the Main Cause of Infertility in Woman* and it was re-presented again at that same year at the ICEGO HOUSTON 2019 International Conference and Exhibition on Gynecology and Obstetrics, that was held on September 28-28th 2019, in Houston, Texas, United States [3].

In all these conferences, the author explained the importance of treating the patient's energy deficiencies to have a good response in the treatment of infertility. Nowadays, not only women, but also men are suffering from the influences of electromagnetic waves that affect the entire population of our planet and could lead to diminish probability of the couple to conceive the baby. For this reason, the author usually orientates the couple that both needs to treat their energy imbalances, even if the laboratorial exams are normal because the problem usually is in the energy level, that is usually not seeing by the naked eyes [3].

Since the implementation in the Flexner report in 1913, all medical schools in the Americas, Europe and Asia have changed their curriculum and only what they could see with the naked eye was considered scientific and everything that was part of the most holistic treatment, where other modes of treatment more natural and alternative methods have been completely banned from medical education. At that time, it was necessary to close more than one hundred schools of homeopathy in the United States and today, we are feeling in our daily practice the difficulties that the doctor himself has in treating his patients because many things related to infertility are at the energy level, invisible to the eye naked and therefore, many current practices are still unable to aim for the desired result because they are not yet treating what is changed, which are the energy changes in our patients, especially those who are dealing with infertility [3,4].

The lack of holistic understanding of the human being was discussed by Fritjof Capra (1975) in the book *The Tao of Physics* where the author explains that everything that exists in our universe is made of energy, including the human being. He shows

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that the different views of Western and Eastern medicine generate a duality of something that should be one thing.

The author claims that what is responsible for the chaos in the world today, regarding the medical treatment of our patients is the lack of deep understanding of what happens at the energy level, not studied by Western medicine doctors, complicating treatments that could be solved with simple treatment of energy rebalancing and dietary changes.

Ignorance of understanding the whole, looking at the patient only from the angle they can see, and ignoring the other part that is also part of the human being, which is their energy, has been creating confusion and a collapse of the health system and the economy in many countries around the world. We can see this in treatments implemented in patients infected with SARS-CoV-2, with this absurd rate of death globally [2,5].

The author wrote an article entitled *Chakra's energy deficiency as the main cause of infertility in women*, reports in her article three clinical cases of patients who underwent in vitro fertilization treatment in Western medicine's perspectives, and were unable to generate the child as expected [3].

Only after simple techniques of changing the diet, rebalancing the internal energies and fulfilling the internal energies of the five massive organs of the theory of the Five Elements of traditional Chinese medicine (Liver, Heart, Spleen, Lung and Kidney), which correspond to the energy centers of the chakras in Ayurvedic medicine, couples were able to have the children they expected with about 30 days after beginning their Chinese medicine's treatment, without having to use IVF techniques, recommended in Western medicine to patient with infertility problems [3].

The lack of understanding of the holistic view of the human beings that is firmly established in energy, before materializing and that all the cells, glands and systems can maintain their proper functions if the internal energy was at its full capacity, could be the major problem nowadays [5].

In a research that the author did in her clinic during 2015 and 2020, studying the energy of the 1000 patient chakras' energy centers, she found that more than 90 percent of her patients are without energy, and that 97 percent are without energy in the kidney or in the second chakra that is responsible for the production of male and female hormones and maintaining the fertility of these patients [2].

If we open the range of information for our doctors and the understanding of the depth of the functioning of our organs and systems at energy level, we can increase in alarming proportions the results of the infertility treatment of our patients, since due to the problems that the electromagnetic waves has caused in humans by reducing the energies of all chakras' energy centers, even the use of hormones can be a

potential risk nowadays, very well explained by the Arndt Schultz Law created in 1888 [6].

In this law, the two German researchers state that the use of drugs in high concentrations reduces the vital energy, (and the hormones are considered highly concentrated). As the author said in her research in Brazil that more than 90% of her patients were in the lowest level of energy, the use of hormones nowadays is considered a drug with potential to induce many side effects on the patient, due to more reduction in this vital energy. In many article written by the author, she is demonstrating other forms of treatment of patients with variety of women's health disorders without need to use hormones, being one of the articles entitled *Chakras's Energy Deficiency as One of the Cause of Menopause Symptoms in Women*. This year, the author was invited to present in the International Conference on Neurology and Neurosurgery that will be held in Singapore in December 2021, being a Keynote speaker, to talk about the neurology changes that could happen with the use of hormones these days [7].

The author will dissert two clinical cases in which the patients were using the hormones as a contraceptive and the second to regulate her menstrual cycle, where she was bleeding almost every day of the month. The first patient presented after two years of continuous use of contraceptive, cavernous sinus thrombosis, being currently treated with anticoagulant and diuretic. The second patient presented with a cerebrovascular accident with paresthesia of the lower and right upper limbs, and presenting alterations in speech. Both patients had major energy deficiencies in the chakras' energy centers, and are currently being treated with gradual recovery in their symptoms and these complications after using hormones were due to the energy deficiency that they have that was important to keep the Blood circulation normally inside the vessels. With the use of hormones (considered highly concentrated medications), the vital energy reduced and the energy important to keep the Blood flowing inside the vessel reduced and caused the blood clot and thrombosis in the first case and the stroke in the second case. In an article written by the author (2021) entitled *Chakras' Energies Deficiencies as One Cause of Abnormal Uterine Bleeding in Women*, the author is explaining in this article that women with abnormal bleeding has chakras' energy deficiencies that is producing internal Heat and the treatment of this condition using Chinese dietary counseling, auricular acupuncture associating with apex ear bloodletting and replenishing the chakras' energy centers with highly diluted medications such as homeopathy according to the theory *Constitutional Homeopathy of the Five Elements Based on Traditional Chinese Medicine* and using crystal based medications was very effective in the treatment of this kind of disturbances in the menstrual cycle [8,9].

Therefore, what our eyes cannot see, which are the energy alterations, are extremely important for the doctors

to understand so they could fully realize to prevent and treat their patients, in different manifestations of diseases and could choose which kind of medication should be used to prevent further complications, as reported in the two cases described above and it was published by the author (2021) in an editorial entitled *Is the Population in the World the Same as in the Past?* [10].

Changes in the curriculum in medical schools must be implemented, as we are teaching our future doctors to treat patients with medications that are potentially harmful to our energy, which are already low, and rules signed in the past, must urgently be rethought so that our future doctors can use medications appropriate to the new black situation in which the population is currently, very different from what happened in the past, due to the modernity process in which our world is suffering and causing deleterious effects on our internal energy, essential for the normal functioning of our organs and systems, to guarantee a healthier future for our population and for all human beings on this planet Earth [10].

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